

RADIOGRAPHIC STUDY OF THE ANTERIOR- POSTERIOR POSITION AND SHAPE OF MENTAL FORAMEN IN IRAQI POPULATION**Rawaa Zaher Hassan Zwain^{*1}, Anwar Hussein Jawad² & Rusul Subhi Hassan³**^{*1}Prosthetic Department, College of Dentistry, Kufa University, Iraq²Department of Prosthodontics, College of Dentistry, Baghdad University, Iraq³Department of Periodontology, College of Dentistry, University of Kufa, Iraq**ABSTRACT**

Accurate information regarding the horizontal location and shape of the mental foramen can have clinical significance, such as reducing complications that may occur during maxillofacial surgical procedures involving the mental area. Geographic variations were reported in these variables. The aim was to study the horizontal position and shape of the mental foramen, as seen on panoramic radiographs of an Iraqi sample, to assess difference in these variables between sexes and age groups, and to assess symmetry of the mental foramen. 246 panoramic radiographs of a random Iraqi sample (126 males, 120 females, average age=46.5 years) were evaluated with regard to the horizontal location, shape and symmetry of the mental foramina. The area with the long axis of the second mandibular premolar, and the round type were the most frequent horizontal location and shape of mental foramen, respectively. Age advancement was found to be associated with an increase in the frequency of more posterior positioning and irregular shape. The horizontal position and shape were asymmetrical in 24.3% and 18.2% of cases, respectively. The most common horizontal location and shape of the mental foramen on panoramic radiographs in this group are with the second premolar, and the round type, respectively. This is in consistence with the findings of previous studies on other populations. The mental foramina have usually symmetrical horizontal locations and shapes.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mental foramen (MF) is a funnel like opening on the lateral surface of the mandible at the terminus of the mandibular canal; it transmits mental nerves and vessels, providing sensory innervations and blood supply respectively (10). Anatomical position and symmetry of MF is of significant importance while administering local anesthesia, treatments of fractures related to parasymphysis area, osteotomies required for orthognathic surgeries, implant placement and fabricating complete denture in mandible etc. (8)(11). Preoperative study of MF is important to prevent damage to the mental nerve which will cause paresthesia, transient or permanent loss of sensation of the lip, chin, and oral mucosa that is often associated with a limited xerostomia (8)(12). Radiographically mental foramen appear as a radiolucent area in lower premolar region & sometimes between the apex of a premolar.(4)(13)(14) the shape of the mental foramen on panoramic radiographs commonly appears as an oval or circular opening on the anteriolateral surface of the mandible. However other rare shapes have been reported in other individuals such as the irregular type (1)(15). Phillips JL reported that anatomically the mental foramen is generally oval shaped with an average size of 4.6 mm horizontally and 3.4 mm vertically, positioned at the apex of the mandibular second premolar in 62.7% of the population (2) (16). A similar study on sixty-six dry mandibles of Nigerians also reported the vertical position of the mental foramen to be in line with the long axis of the second premolar teeth, mostly round in shape and often symmetric (2) (24). Mental Nerve emerges from the mental foramen & innervates the soft tissues of the chin, lower lip & gingiva on the each side of mandible (4) (25). The usual horizontal (anterior-posterior) position of the mental foramen has been reported to be between the apices of the mandibular premolars in some populations (1) (15) and below the mandibular second premolar in others (27). However, individual variation could lead to other locations ranging from the apex of the canine to the apex of the mesiobuccal root of the mandibular first molar (1) (19).

The mental foramen is considered as a stable anatomical landmark in the human skull. It is anatomically stationed at 11–15 mm superior to the base of the mandible (3) (20). The accurate identification of MF position and AL can be very challenging. Various techniques have been applied for determining the precise position of MF and AL before performing surgical procedures. These techniques include, manual palpation, direct visualization during surgery, cadaveric dissection, panoramic radiographs, peri-apical radiographs, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Computed Tomography (CT) and Cone-Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT). Most techniques come with limitations such as cost, radiation exposure and magnification (7) (21)

The MF changes its position with age, which is also influenced by demographic factors like sex and the ethnicity. The variations in the position of MF can be attributed to the forward growth of the mandible during the craniofacial development and the differential rates of development of the bone and the periosteum. (8)(22)

The visualization of mental foramen in intraoral radiograph is difficult due to its position below the edge of the film. The proper placement of film inside the patient mouth during radiographic examination is difficult because of several factors such as limited mouth opening, mandibular tori, a shallow floor of mouth & malaligned teeth. Most of the time mental foramen cannot be captured in periapical radiograph due to its oblique direction in the mesiodistal & inferiosuperiorplanes (4) (27). Any foramina in addition to the MF found in body of mandible are known as accessory MF. It may not present in some of the populations but both MF and accessory MF are important landmarks in surgical procedures (6) (26)

2. Materials And Methods

Three hundred panoramic radiographs were randomly selected from over-many-year records of Iraqi patients .their viewing qualities were regarded to be optimal and deemed of a good diagnostic quality. This was because the manufacturer's operation manuals were followed. The 246panoramic radiographs were the final number of radiographs included in the present study after excluding 54 radiographs due to varies reasons:

- Patients aged less than 18 years.
- The presence of a radiolucent lesion or periodontal lesions, or a missing or an impacted tooth, or a crowding and spacing anywhere in the area extending from the lower right first molar to the lower left first molar.
- Patient with history of orthodontic treatment of lower arch crowding and spacing.
- Poor film quality Anterior-posterior position of the mental foramen. A longitudinal axis of each mandibular premolar was drawn on both sides utilizing the drawing ruler of the software. Using the same definitions found in the literature (AlKhateeb et al., 2007; Haghanifar & Rokouei, 2009), the anterior-posterior position of each mental foramen was then recorded in relation to the longitudinal axis of the nearest tooth as follows(Fig.2.1):

- Position 1: Anterior to the first premolar
 Position 2: In line with the first premolar
 Position 3: Between the first and second premolars
 Position 4: In line with the second premolar
 Position 5: Between the second premolar and first molar
 Position 6: In line with the first molar.

Shape of the mental foramen. The shape of the foramen was recorded as round or oval or irregular. This was achieved by using the drawing ruler of the software to outline the external circumference of each mental foramen.

Fig (2.1) Schematic representation of the numeric expression of the mental foramen position relative to the teeth

3. Results

The included 246 panoramic radiographs were analyzed on both sides, and were 126 for males and 120 for females with a 1:1.05 male-to-female ratio. The age ranging from 18 to 56 years. Table 3.3 and 3.4 detail the horizontal position and the shape of the mental foramen.

Horizontal (Anterior–posterior) position.

The most common horizontal position for the mental foramen in this Iraqi sample was in line with the long axis of second mandibular premolar (48.37%) (Fig. 3.1)

Fig. (3.1) A panoramic radiograph showing symmetrical anterior-posterior location and symmetrical shape of mental foramina. with the position in the area between the long axes of mandibular premolars being the second most common (40.04%) (Fig. 3.2)

Fig. (3.2) A panoramic radiograph showing symmetrical anterior-posterior location and asymmetrical shape of mental foramina

A position for the mental foramen anterior to the first premolar was not observed. The most frequent horizontal position was noticed to be not different between right and left sides (Table 3.3), and among males and females (Table 3.4).

In 186 cases (75.6%), the position of mental foramina anterioposteriorly were symmetrical (Fig. 3.1) and the remainder 60 cases (24.4%) were asymmetrical (Fig. 3.3). Age advancement was noticed to position the mental foramen in more posterior locations (Table 3.1)

Fig. (3.3) A panoramic radiograph showing asymmetrical anterior-posterior location and symmetrical shape of mental foramina.

Age advancement was noticed to position the mental foramen in more posterior locations (Fig. 3.1).

Table (3.1) A clustered graph showing the effect of advancing age on the anterior-posterior location of the mental foramen (n=492 cases)

The shape of mental foramen:

The most common (40.85%) shape of the mental foramen in this Iraqi sample was irregular type (Fig. 3.4), with the round one being the second most common (35.36%) (Fig. 3.4). This most frequent shape was not different between right and left sides (Table 3.3), and among males and females (Table 3.4). Age advancement was noticed to provide more irregular and round shape of the mental foramen (table.3.2).

table. (3.2) A clustered graph showing the effect of advancing age on the shape of the mental foramen (n=492 cases)

(Table 3.3): Distribution of the horizontal position and shape of mental foramen on both sides by sex (n=492 sides)

radiographic feature of the foramen	sex								total	%
	male				female					
	right	%	left	%	right	%	left	%		
AP position										
anterior to LP1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
in the line with LP1	4	3.17	3	2.3	3	2.5	2	1.6	12	2.43
between LP1 and LP2	48	38	60	47.51	44	36.66	45	37.5	197	40.04
in the line with LP2	59	46.3	54	42.85	64	53.3	61	50.8	238	48.37
between LP2 and LM1	12	9.5	9	7.14	9	7.5	12	10	42	8.53
in the line with LM1	3	2.38	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0.6
total	126	100	126	100	120	100	120	100	492	100
shape										
round	48	38.1	48	38.1	39	32.5	39	32.5	174	35.36
oval	33	26.2	21	16.7	33	27.5	30	25	117	23.78
irregular	45	35.7	57	45.2	48	40	51	42.5	201	40.85
total	126	100	126	100	120	100	120	100	492	100

AP= anterior-posterior; LP1= lower first premolar; LP2= lower second premolar; LM1= lower first molar

Table (3.4) Frequency of the horizontal position and shape of mental foramen (by sex) as seen in the present study (n=492sides).

radiographic feature of the foramen	sex				total	%
	male		female			
	male	%	female	%		
AP position						
anterior to LP1	0	0	0	0	0	0
in the line with LP1	7	2.77	5	2.08	12	2.43
between LP1 and LP2	108	42.85	89	37.08	197	40.04
in the line with LP2	113	44	125	52.08	238	48.37
between LP2 and LM1	21	8.3	21	8.75	42	8.53
in the line with LM1	3	1.19	0	0	3	0.6
total	252	100	240	100	492	100
shape						
round	96	38.09	78	32.5	174	35.36
oval	54	21.42	63	26.25	117	23.78
irregular	102	40.47	99	41.25	201	40.85
total	252	100	240	100	492	100

AP= anterior-posterior; LP1= lower first premolar; LP2= lower second premolar; LM1= lower first molar.

In 201 cases (81.7%), mental foramina in both sides were symmetrical in shape (Fig. 3.1) and the remainder 45 cases (18.3%) were asymmetrical (Fig. 3.2). Females (82.5%) recorded more symmetry in the shape of mental foramina than males (80.95%) but the difference was statistically insignificant (Table 3.5).

Table (3.5) the horizontal position and shape of mental foramen by sex and symmetry (n=246 cases)

			symmetrical	%	assymetrical	%
sex difference	antero-posterior position	male	90	48.38	36	60
		female	96	51.6	24	30
		total	186	100	60	100
	shape	male	102	50.8	24	53.4
		female	99	49.2	21	46.6
		total	201	100	45	100
age groups	antero-posterior position	11_40	120	64.52	48	80
		>40	66	35.48	12	20
		total	186	100	60	100
	shape	11_40	120	59.7	36	80
		>40	81	40.3	9	20
		total	201	100	45	100

4. DISCUSSION

Knowledge concerning the exact anterior-posterior location and shape of the mental foramen is of great clinical importance. It would lead to an accurate local anesthetic technique needed in many dental procedures and would protect the mental neurovascular bundle in different oral surgical procedures. Additionally, good interpretation of anatomical landmarks in oral pathology and forensics can be aided (Neo, 1989) (44). For all of the above mentioned reasons, the horizontal location and other characteristics of the mental foramen have been studied utilizing panoramic radiographs or dry skulls. Although studies reported a strong correlation and insignificant differences between measurements using comparative studies on dry skulls and those using radiographs (Al Jasser & Nwoku, 1998(29); Phillips et al., 1990(16); Wang et al.1986 (52).; Yosue & Brooks, 1989a) (53), a cautious use of panoramic radiographs in reporting absolute measurements or relative comparisons has been advised (Laster et al., 2005)(40).

In this study, the anterior posterior position and shape of the mental foramen in a selected Iraqi population were studied using panoramic radiographs rather than other plane films such as periapical radiographs which would not provide the wide field of mandible view. Consequently, more accurate interpretation of shape and location of the mental foramen in both the horizontal and vertical dimensions are allowed by using panoramic radiographs (Yosue & Brooks, 1989b (54); Phillips et al., 1992a, 1992b) (18·27). Similarly, our exclusion criteria aimed to avoid any factor that may affect accurate determination of the horizontal location or shape of the mental foramen such as periodontal lesions or history of orthodontic treatment which could lead to tooth migration. Poor film quality could also provide inaccurate or distorted shape of the foramen. In the same way, only patients over the age of 18 years were included because we needed patients with completed skeletal growth.

Studies reported in the literature concerning the anterior-posterior localization of the mental foramen have been used in two different methods namely by relating the foramen to adjacent teeth or to the mandibular body. Relating the mental foramen position to the teeth is more popular in all over the world (Al Jasser & Nwoku, 1998(29); Aktekin et al(17)., 2003; Cutright et al2003(34).; Green1987(36); Matheson et al., 1986 (41); Moiseiwitsch1998 (13); Mwaniki & Hassanali1992(43); Ngeow & Yuzawati2003(23); Olasoji et al.2004 (46); Phillips et al., 1990, 1992a, 1992b) (16·18·27) and more convenient clinically (Green) but may be influenced by congenital or environmental factors such as race, diet, and age which have their detrimental effects on teeth alignment (i.e. malocclusion) or size (i.e. mesiodistal width). The other method is more reliable as it relates the foramen to specific points and ratios on the mandible (Apinhasmit et al., 2006(31); Laster et al.2005 (40); Oguz & Bozkir, 2002) (45). However, this later method is more time-consuming which is not convenient for busy clinicians.

Different anterior-posterior positions and shapes of mental foramen have recently been reported to be existed between population of different or even of the same geography (Ari et al.2005(32); Igbigbi & Lebona2005(38); Mbajorgu et al.1998(42); Souaga et al2004(50). Additionally, positions of the mental foramen other than the two most common described above and consequently variable characteristics were attributed to the possible lag

in developmental changes in its location during postnatal life. This attribution was drawn because the very early position of the mental foramen was found to be in the alveolar bone between the primary canine and first molar (Kjaer, 1989) (39).

In our series of 246 panoramic radiographs the anterior-posterior location of the mental foramen was most commonly (48.37%) the position in line with the long axis of second mandibular premolar, with (40.04%) in the area between the long axis of first and second mandibular premolars being the second most common; thus 88.41% of foramina lie at either these two positions. Therefore, about 88.41% success rate of the mental or incisive nerve block, compared to 95% reported on a sample of northern Jordanians (Al-Khateeb et al., 2007)(15), could be expected if the needle insertion point is placed at either of or between these two points. Studies on a North American white population (Moiseiwitsch), Northern Nigerian adults (Fishel et al.1976(19); Olasoji et al.2004(46), Iranian adults (Haghanifar & Rokouei)2009(37), northern Jordanian adults (Al-Khateeb et al., 2007)(15) and most Caucasian populations from different countries (Cutright et al.2003(34); Laster et al.2005(40); Moiseiwitsch1998(13); Phillips et al., 1990, 1992a, 1992b(16·18·27)) reported the area between the two premolars as the most common location of the mental foramen. These findings disagree with our results.

In this study, we have found no case with a horizontal position of the mental foramen anterior to the first premolar. This agrees with previous studies in some regional countries such as Jordan (Al-Khateeb et al., 2007)(15), Saudi Arabia (al-Khateeb et al., 1994)(30) and Iran (Haghanifar & Rokouei)2009(37). Some of these previous studies (al-Khateeb et al., 1994, 2007)(30·15) reported that in males the most frequent anterior-posterior position of the mental foramen was between the first and second mandibular premolar teeth, and in females along the line of the second mandibular premolar with no reference to the differences between right and left sides, as the right and left sides were not considered separately. Other previous studies (Al Jasser & Nwoku1996·1998(28·29); Haghanifar & Rokouei)2009(37) reported that on the right side, the commonest position of the mental foramen was between the first and second premolars, and on the left side it was in line with the second premolar. Additionally, they (Haghanifar & Rokouei) reported that the position in line with the second premolar was the most common one among males and the position between the first and second premolars was the most common one among females.

However, these previous studies disagree with our findings in some of the aspects which have indicated that the most frequent anterior-posterior position was not that much different between right and left sides, and among males and females. This might indicate geography related differences in the degree of bilateralism and sexual dimorphism in the horizontal location of the mental foramen (Ari et al.)(32).

Regarding the effect of age on the anterior-posterior location of the mental foramen, Age advancement was noticed to position the mental foramen in more posterior locations. Our later finding also agrees with those of previous studies (Agthong et al.2005(9); Al-Khateeb et al., 2007)(15) which attributed this posterior shift in positioning to the anterior tooth drift that occurs due to the expected age-related attrition of interproximal surfaces of teeth. We have found that the position of the mental foramen was asymmetrical anteroposteriorly in about one quarter of the cases

This figure of frequency of asymmetry is higher than that reported in Saudi Arabia (Al Jasser & Nwoku, 1998(29)) and North America (Moiseiwitsch) but lower than that reported in Jordan (Al-Khateeb et al., 2007)(15) where sex and age differences, and the statistical significance of these differences were not considered. In this study, difference in the rate of symmetry in the anterior-posterior location of mental foramen was found to be statistically significant differences between males and females. This disagrees with previous studies on other populations (Haghanifar & Rokouei) where no statistically significant difference was found between males and females in symmetry of the horizontal location of mental foramen.

In the present study, we observed a round-shaped mental foramen in 35.36% of the cases and an oval-shaped foramen in 23.78%. These figures are not close to those reported in some regional countries (Al-Khateeb et al., 2007) (15) and disagree with results reported on some populations in other parts of the world (Singh & Srivastav, 2010)(49). However, our findings disagree with studies on other populations (Agarwal & Gupta, 2011(5); Gershenson et al., 1986(35); Igbigbi & Lebona2005(38); Mbajorgu et al.1998(42); Probodra & Nanayakkara, 2006(47); Souaga et al.2004(50)), which showed that the most frequent shape was oval. Additionally, we have found that this most frequent shape was not different between right and left sides, and among males and females. However, age advancement was noticed to provide an increase in the frequency of more irregular shape of the mental foramen. These later results found in this study concerning side, sex and age differences were not investigated in most of the previous studies on various populations (Al Jasser & Nwoku, 1998(29); al-Khateeb et al., 1994, 2007(30·15); Mbajorgu et al.1998(42); Oguz & Bozkir2002(45); Olasoji et al.2004(46).; Phillips et al., 1990, 1992a(16·18); Yosue & Brooks, 1989a(53)). it is important to mention that the remarkable portion of

round-shaped mental foramen was attributed by some (Schulze et al., 2000(48)) to possible technical problems that could occur during taking panoramic radiographs such as magnification and positioning inaccuracies. Alternatively, the most common shape of the mental foramen might be geography-related (Ari et al.2005)(32). (Khateeb et al., 2007)(15). In this study, statistically significant difference was found between old and young age groups in the frequency of symmetry of the shape of mental foramen, in favor of the older group.

Generally, the developmental and functional facts are likely to explain the variability and asymmetry in the horizontal position and shape of mental foramen. The mandible from developmental and functional point of views consists of several skeletal subunits; a primary neural subunit and secondary functional subunits (Sperber, 2001)(51). Regarding the asymmetry of the mental foramen position, it is attributed to different functional secondary subunits such as the alveolar, coronoid, angular, condylar process, and chin. These secondary functional subunits are attached to the nearly symmetric primary neural subunit which is a representation of the bone surrounding the mandibular nerve or the primitive mandible. This primitive mandible is formed in the first branchial arch as the first osteogenic center of the mandibular body that arises lateral to the Meckel's cartilage and to the mandibular nerve, and rapidly forms a groove that surrounds the nerve (Captier et al., 2006)(33). Finally, although research results and, functional and developmental facts may explain the variability and asymmetry in the anterior-posterior position and shape of mental foramen, the reason of this variability and asymmetry between people of different races, geographies, ages and sexes has probably not clearly explained yet. Additionally, the study is not without limitations. It was a cross-sectional, epidemiologic retrospective study, and we selected only one area in Iraq due to limitation of time, funds and communication with Iraqi universities and hospitals. The small sample size was an additional limitation. Therefore, we feel that broad generalizations of the findings are not possible, and a further study incorporating a nationally representative sample is needed to confirm the results of the present study.

In conclusion, the most common horizontal location and shape of the mental foramen on panoramic radiographs in this group of Iraqis are in line with the long axis of second mandibular premolar, and irregular type respectively. This is consistent with the results of previous studies in other populations. The mental foramina, in the present Iraqi sample, have usually symmetrical horizontal location and shapes on both sides of the mandible.

REFERENCES

- Al-Shayyab, M.H., Alsoleihat, F., Dar-Odeh, N.S., Ryalat, S. and Baqain, Z.H., 2015. The Mental Foramen I: Radiographic Study of the Anterior-Posterior Position and Shape in Iraqi Population. *International Journal of Morphology*, 33(1).
- Bello, S.A., Adeoye, J.A., Ighile, N. and Ikimi, N.U., 2018. Mental foramen size, position and symmetry in a multi-ethnic, urban black population: Radiographic evidence. *Journal of oral & maxillofacial research*, 9(4).
- Rani, A., Kanjani, V., Kanjani, D. and Annigeri, R.G., 2019. Morphometric assessment of mental foramen for gender prediction using panoramic radiographs in the West Bengal population-A retrospective digital study. *Journal of Advanced Clinical and Research Insights*, 6(3), pp.63-66.
- Thakur, S.N., Mishra, M.K., Pandey, B., Singh, H. and Mishra, S., 2019. Radiographic study of mental foramen in Chitwan population. *Journal of Chitwan Medical College*, 9(4), pp.35-38.
- Currie, C.C., Meechan, J.G., Whitworth, J.M., Carr, A. and Corbett, I.P., 2016. Determination of the mental foramen position in dental radiographs in 18–30 year olds. *Dentomaxillofacial Radiology*, 45 (1), p.20150195.
- Agarwal, D. R. & Gupta, S. B. Morphometric analysis of mental foramen in human mandible of south Gujarat. *People's J. Sci. Res.*, 4:15-8, 2011.
- Al-Juboori, M., Al-Wakeel, H., SuWen, F. and Yun, C.M., 2014. Mental foramen location and its implication in dental treatment plan. *World Journal of Medicine and Medical Science Research*, 2(3), pp.35-42.
- Al-Mahalawy, H., Al-Aithan, H., Al-Kari, B., Al-Jandan, B. and Shujaat, S., 2017. Determination of the position of mental foramen and frequency of anterior loop in Saudi population. A retrospective CBCT study. *The Saudi Dental Journal*, 29(1), pp.29-35.
- Jayam, R., Sameeulla, S., Maddhuru, R., Vijaykumar, B., Suman, S.V. and Praveen, K.S., Assessment of Superio-Inferior, Medio-Lateral Position and Symmetry of Mental Foramen and Its Correlation with Age and Gender among South Indian Population Using Panoramic Radiographs.
- Agthong, S.; Huanmanop, T. & Chentanez, V. Anatomical variations of the supraorbital, infraorbital, and mental foramina related to gender and side. *J. Oral Maxillofac. Surg.*, 63(6):800-4, 2005.
- Gada S K, Nagda S J. Assessment of Position and Bilateral Symmetry of Occurrence of Mental Foramen in Dentate in Asian population. *JClinDiagnRes* 2014; 8(2):203-5.
- Gada S K, Nagda S J. Assessment of Position and Bilateral Symmetry of Occurrence of Mental Foramen in Dentate in Asian population. *JClinDiagnRes* 2014; 8(2):203-5.

- Swamy NN, Nagaraj T, Ghouse N, Jagadish CD, Sreelakshmi N, Goswami RD. Radiographic study of mental foramen type and position in Bangalore population. *J Med Radiol Pathol Surg* 2015;1:5-8.
- Jamdade AS, Yadav S, Bhayana R, Khare V, Pardhe N, Mathur N. Radiographic localization of mental foramen in a selected Indian population. *Innovat J Med Health Sci*. 2013; 3(5): 249-53.
- Moiseiwitsch JR. Position of mental foramen in a North American, White population. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod* 1998;85:457-60. [DOI]
- Phillips JL, Weller RN, Kulild JC. The mental foramen: 2. Radiographic position in Relation to the mandibular second premolar. *J Endod*. 1992;18:271-4. [DOI]
- Al-Khateeb, T.; Al-Hadi Hamasha, A. & Ababneh, K. T. Position of the mental foramen in a northern regional Jordanian population. *Surg. Radiol. Anat.*, 29(3):231-7, 2007.
- Phillips JL, Weller RN, Kulild JC. The mental foramen: 1. Size, orientation, and positional relationship to the mandibular second premolar. *J Endod*. 1990 May;16(5):221-3.
- Aktekin, M.; Celik, H. M.; Celik, H. H.; Aldur, M. M. & Aksit, M. D. Studies on the location of the mental foramen in Turkish mandibles. *Morphologie*, 87(277):17-9, 2003.
- Phillips, J. L.; Weller, R. N. & Kulild, J. C. The mental foramen: 2. Radiographic position in relation to the mandibular second premolar. *J. Endod.*, 18(6):271-4, 1992a.
- Fishel, D.; Buchner, A.; Hershkowith, A. & Kaffe, I. Roentgenologic study of the mental foramen. *Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol.*, 41(5):682-6, 1976.
- Al-Shamout R, Ammouh M, Alrbata R, Al-Hababha A. Age and gender differences in gonial angle, ramus height and bigonial width in dentate subjects. *Pak Oral Dent J* 2012;32:81-7. and Haghanifar S, Rokouei M. Radiographic evaluation of the mental foramen in a selected Iranian population. *Indian J Dent Res* 2009;20:150-2.
- Aminoshariae, A., Su, A., Kulild, J.C., 2014. Determination of the location of the mental foramen: a critical review. *J. Endodontics* 40 (4), 471–475.
- Bhata ZA, Chalkoob AH, Malik AMD. Mental foramen position, shape and size of mental foramen in adult human mandibles. *Int J Health Sci Res*. 2017; 7(2):153-156.
- Ngeow WC, Yuzawati Y. The location of the mental foramen in a selected Malay population. *J Oral Sci*. 2003 Sep;45(3): 171-5.
- Ukoha UU, KE Umeasalujo, UC Ofoego, OC Ejimofor, HC Nzeako, CG Edokwe. Position, shape and direction of the mental foramen in mandibles in South-Eastern Nigeria. *Int J Biomed Res*. 2013 Sep;4(9):499-503.
- Roy PP, Ambali MP, Doshi MA, Jadhav SD. Variation in the position shape and direction of mental foramen in dry mandible. *Int J Anat Res*. 2014;2(2):418-20.
- Rajani Singh Srivastav AK (2010). Study of position, shape, size and incidence of mental foramen and accessory mental foramen in Indian adult skulls. *Int. J. Morphol.*, 28:1141-1146
- Phillips JL, Weller RN, Kulild JC. The mental foramen: 3. Size and position on panoramic radiograph. *J Endod.*, 18:383-6, 1992b.
- Al Jasser, N. M. & Nwoku, A. L. Radiographic study of the mental foramen in Saudi females. *Saudi Med. J.*, 17:471-4, 1996.
- Al Jasser, N. M. & Nwoku, A. L. Radiographic study of the mental foramen in a selected Saudi population. *Dentomaxillofac. Radiol.*, 27(6):341-3, 1998.
- Al-Khateeb, T. L.; Odukoya, O. & el-Hadidy, M. A. Panoramic radiographic study of mental foramen locations in Saudi Arabians. *Afr. Dent. J.*, 8:16-9, 1994.
- Apinhasmit, W.; Methathathip, D.; Chompoopong, S. & Sangvichien, S. Mental foramen in Thais: an anatomical variation related to gender and side. *Surg. Radiol. Anat.*, 28(5):529-33, 2006.
- Ari, I.; Kafa, I. M.; Basar, Z. & Kurt, M. A. The localization and anthropometry of mental foramen on late Byzantine mandibles. *Coll. Antropol.*, 29(1):233-6, 2005.
- Captier, G.; Lethuillier, J.; Oussaid, M.; Canovas, F. & Bonnel, F. Neural symmetry and functional asymmetry of the mandible. *Surg. Radiol. Anat.*, 28(4):379-86, 2006.
- Cutright, B.; Quillopa, N. & Schubert, W. An anthropometric analysis of the key foramina for maxillofacial surgery. *J. Oral Maxillofac. Surg.*, 61(3):354-7, 2003.
- Gershenson, A.; Nathan, H. & Luchansky, E. Mental foramen and mental nerve: changes with age. *Acta Anat. (Basel)*, 126(1):21-6, 1986.
- Green, R. M. The position of the mental foramen: a comparison between the southern (Hong Kong) Chinese and other ethnic and racial groups. *Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol.*, 63(3):287-90, 1987.
- Haghanifar, S. & Rokouei, M. Radiographic evaluation of the mental foramen in a selected Iranian population. *Indian J. Dent. Res.*, 20(2):150-2, 2009.
- Igbigbi, P. S. & Lebona, S. The position and dimensions of the mental foramen in adult Malawian mandibles. *West Afr. J. Med.*, 24(3):184-9, 2005.

- Kjaer, I. Formation and early prenatal location of the human mental foramen. *Scand. J. Dent. Res.*, 97(1):1-7, 1989.
- Laster, W. S.; Ludlow, J. B.; Bailey, L. J. & Hershey, H. G. Accuracy of measurements of mandibular anatomy and prediction of asymmetry in panoramic radiographic images. *Dentomaxillofac. Radiol.*, 34(6):343-9, 2005.
- Matheson, B. R.; Blanton, P. L.; Rivera-Hidalgo, F.; Rees, T. D.; Bradley, R. E. & Dill, R. Utilization of an intraoral landmark to localize the mental foramen. *J. Dent. Res.*, 63A:278-80, 1986.
- Mbajjorgu, E. F.; Mawera, G.; Asala, S. A. & Zivanovic, S. Position of the mental foramen in adult black Zimbabwean mandibles: a clinical anatomical study. *Cent. Afr. J. Med.*, 44(2):24-30, 1998.
- Mwaniki, D. L. & Hassanali, J. The position of mandibular and mental foramina in Kenyan African mandibles. *East Afr. Med. J.*, 69(4):210-3, 1992.
- Neo, J. Position of the mental foramen in Singaporean Malays and Indians. *Anesth. Prog.*, 36(6):276-8, 1989.
- Oguz, O. & Bozkir, M. G. Evaluation of location of mandibular and mental foramina in dry, young, adult human male, dentulous mandibles. *West Indian Med. J.*, 51(1):14-6, 2002.
- Olasoji, H. O.; Tahir, A.; Ekanem, A. U. & Abubakar, A. A. Radiographic and anatomic locations of mental foramen in northern Nigerian adults. *Niger. Postgrad. Med. J.*, 11(3):230-3, 2004.
- Prabodra, L. B. L. & Nanayakkara, B. G. The position, dimension and morphological variations of mental foramen in mandibles. *Galle Med. J.*, 11:13-5, 2006.
- Schulze, R.; Schalldach, F. & d'Hoedt, B. Effect of positioning errors on magnification factors in the mandible in digital panorama imaging. *Mund. Kiefer. Gesichtschir.*, 4(3):164-70, 2000.
- Singh, R. & Srivastav, A. K. Study of position, shape, size and incidence of mental foramen and accessory mental foramen in Indian adult human skulls. *Int. J. Morphol.*, 28(4):1141-6, 2010.
- Souaga, K.; Adou, A. & Angoh, Y. Topographical and morphological study of the mandibular foramen in black Africans from the Ivory Coast. *Odontostomatol. Trop.*, 27(105):17-21, 2004.
- Sperber, G. *Craniofacial Development*. London, B. C. Decker, 2001.
- Wang, T. M.; Shih, C.; Liu, J. C. & Kuo, K. J. A clinical and anatomical study of the location of the mental foramen in adult Chinese mandibles. *Acta Anat. (Basel)*, 126(1):29-33, 1986.
- Yosue, T. & Brooks, S. L. The appearance of mental foramina on panoramic radiographs. I. Evaluation of patients. *Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol.*, 68(3):360-4, 1989a.
- Yosue, T. & Brooks, S. L. The appearance of mental foramina on panoramic and periapical radiographs. II. Experimental evaluation. *Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol.*, 68(4):488-92, 1989b.